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Research Article

**LEFT VENTRICULAR DIASTOLIC DYSFUNCTION IN
ASYMPTOMATIC TYPE II DIABETES MELLITUS
PATIENTS PRESENTED TO D.H.Q TEACHING HOSPITAL
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Muhammad Shafique⁵, Dr Muhammad Asad⁶**¹Consultant cardiologist District Headquarter Teaching Hospital Dera Ismail Khan,²Assistant professor medical unit District Headquarter Teaching Hospital Dera Ismail Khan, ³House job District Headquarter Teaching Hospital Dera Ismail Khan, ⁴Demonstrator Gomal Medical College dera ismail khan, ⁵Associate Professor District Headquarter Teaching Hospital Dera Ismail Khan, ⁶Resident doctor medical unit District Headquarter Teaching Hospital Dera Ismail Khan,**Article Received:** January 2020 **Accepted:** February 2020 **Published:** March 2020**Abstract:**

Aim & Background: Diabetes mellitus is a growing disease all over the world. Left untreated it can lead to serious health problems. The aim of the study is to determine the frequency of left ventricular diastolic dysfunction in asymptomatic type II diabetes mellitus patients in D.H.Q teaching hospital Dera Ismail Khan Pakistan.

Methodology: This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted in cardiology department D.H.Q teaching hospital Dera Ismail Khan Pakistan. The study population was stratified according to hospital departments and 200 patients fulfilling the inclusion/exclusion criteria were included in the study. Data was analyzed through SPSS version 20.

Results: Among 200 participants Frequency of diastolic dysfunction was 116(58%) in the study population while 84(42%) have no diastolic dysfunction. Diastolic dysfunction rate was high in patients with longer duration of DM.

Conclusion: Left ventricular diastolic dysfunction rate is higher among asymptomatic type II diabetes mellitus patients. Routinely echocardiography should be performed in asymptomatic DM patients to assess left ventricular function.

Key Words: Type II DM, diastolic dysfunction, heart failure.

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INTRODUCTION:

Diabetes mellitus is a growing disease all over the world. In developing countries, the increase in incidence of diabetes mellitus is 170% as compared to 47% in developed countries. In Pakistan prevalence of diabetes is high 13.14%¹⁵. Diabetes mellitus is a risk factor in the development of heart failure⁹. When it comes to function of the heart systolic function of left ventricle affected later than diastolic function in asymptomatic type II DM,² long term complication is diabetic cardiomyopathy. While discussing the causes of heart failure in DM most commonly it is due to coronary artery disease and if there is no coronary artery disease or hypertension to explain cardiac muscle abnormality then diabetic cardiomyopathy is the cause⁹. Left ventricular diastolic dysfunction is affected earlier than systolic dysfunction in the development of congestive heart failure. According to Greenberg B diastolic dysfunction is an independent predictor in determining risk of HF, for every unit increase in E/e > 15 there risk for HF increases 3%³. Asymptomatic diastolic dysfunction has more prevalence than symptomatic HF. At presentation the symptoms of diastolic dysfunction are difficult to be distinguished from that of systolic dysfunction⁷. Common symptoms include edema, exercise intolerance, orthopnea, and paroxysmal nocturnal dyspnea⁶. In these patients left ventricular end diastolic volume (LVEDV) does not increase on exertion because the chamber stiffness in these patients of diastolic dysfunction, as a result stroke volume decreases, that's why the early symptom to present with oftenly is exercise intolerance⁴. Left ventricular diastolic dysfunction can be assessed by using Doppler echocardiography. Patients with DM but asymptomatic and preserved left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF) may have diastolic dysfunction as assessed with echocardiography⁵. It is best to do echocardiography routinely in asymptomatic DM patients as it is a simple non-invasive tool and yield much about diastolic dysfunction⁶.

In a study it is stated that diastolic dysfunction is present in 64% of the patients with DM⁷. Another study stated that there is a significant association between diastolic dysfunction and DM, in this study the frequency of diastolic dysfunction was 54.33 % in DM patients⁸.

The aim of our study is to determine the frequency of asymptomatic diastolic dysfunction in type II diabetes mellitus patients with normal systolic function presenting to cardiology department D.H.Q DIK Pakistan.

It is reported that there is high frequency of diastolic dysfunction among DM patients, but in

clinical practice physician do not advise echocardiography as a screening test for cardiac evaluation of diabetic patients. In Pakistan no such study is available for evaluation of diastolic dysfunction in diabetics which results in underdiagnosed and undertreated patients. The result of this study may help in identifying the burden of disease in diabetic patients and to establish local guidelines.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A criterion was made, in this criteria patient with type II DM (defined as fasting blood glucose greater than or equal to 126mg/dl or on anti-diabetic drugs) between the age 40 and 55 years of both genders, presenting with normal left ventricular systolic function on echocardiography, were included in the study.

Patients with hypertension(BP greater than 140/90 or on antihypertensive medication), chronic renal failure(serum creatinine > 1.2 or blood urea >50 mg/dl), patients with evidence of chronic liver disease(alanine aminotransferase > 40 iu/l, aspartate aminotransferase > 40 iu/l), cardiomyopathy (EF < 50%), CAD (excluded by history of angina, chestpain, electrocardiogram changes) and patients with evidence of valvular heart disease were excluded from study. A total of 200 patients participated.an informed consent was taken from the patients.

All the patients underwent resting transthoracic 2-dimensional echocardiography (TTE) and Doppler imaging to assess left ventricular diastolic dysfunction. A TTE with pulsed waved Doppler evaluation of transmitral inflow and Tissue Doppler Imaging (TDI) were performed to minimize the errors in assessing diastolic dysfunction. Echocardiography was performed in harmonic imaging mode by vivid 7 pro machine according to standard protocol. Pulsed wave (PW) Doppler derived transmitral inflow velocities were obtained in the apical 4-chamber view, with the sample volume placed at the tip of mitral valve leaflets. Measurements included the early diastolic rapid filling(E-wave) and atrial contraction late filling(A-wave) velocities ratio (E/A ratio), isovolumetric relaxation time (IVRT) and deceleration time (DT) were noted. For TDI, the mitral annulus velocity was obtained with a 2mm sample volume placed at the lateral side and septal side of the mitral annulus. Diastolic dysfunction was labeled according to AHA diastolic dysfunction guidelines published in 2009 in journal of American society of echocardiography. It states that diastolic dysfunction is present when early diastolic rapid filling(E-wave) and atrial contraction late filling(A-wave) velocities ratio (E/A ratio) <1 or >2.

Stage 2(pseudo-normal) is differentiated from normal by E/e ratio<8(normal) and >10(pseudo-normal). Deceleration time (DT) <150 or >250ms. Isovolumetric relaxation time (IVRT) <60 or >100ms, and ejection fraction >50%. LVEF (systolic function) was calculated by modified simpson's method; and LVEF greater than or equal to 50% was considered as normal.

Data Analysis

The data was analyzed by using SPSS version20. Quantitative variables like age were presented as mean plus minus SD. Qualitative variables like gender and diastolic dysfunction are presented in form of frequency and percentages. Data is stratified for duration of DM.

RESULTS:

200 patients fulfilling the inclusion/exclusion criteria were included in the study to determine the frequency of asymptomatic diastolic dysfunction with normal LV systolic function.

Gender distribution of the patients was done which showed that 110(55%) were male and 90(45%) were female.

Age distribution of the patients was done which showed that 31(15.50%) were between 40-45

years, 63(31.50%) were between 46-40 and 106(53%) were between 51-55 years of age, mean age of the study population was 49.84 ± 4.2 years. Frequency of diastolic dysfunction was 116(58%) in the study population while 84(42%) have no diastolic dysfunction.

In our study population 63%(n= 126) patients had duration of DM between 4-9 years and 37%(N=74) had between 10-14 years. There were 84 smokers.

Stratification for gender was done, out of 116 cases of diastolic dysfunction, 64 were male while 52 were females, for which p value was 0.92.

Stratification for age was done, out of 116 cases of diastolic dysfunction, 14 were between 40-45 years of age, 33 were between 46-50 years of age, 33 were between 46-50 years of age and 69 were between 51-55 years of age.

Stratification for duration of DM was done, out of 116 cases of diastolic dysfunction, 58 had duration of DM between 4-9 years and 58 had duration of DM between 10-14 years.

Stratification for smoker was done, out of 116 cases of diastolic dysfunction 63 were smokers and 53 were non-smoker, p value was 0.001.

TABLE NO 1: Distribution of diastolic dysfunction by gender.

	Dysfunction		Total	P-value
	YES	NO		
Male	64 (58.2%)	46 (41.8%)	110 (100.0%)	0.954
Female	52 (57.8%)	38 (42.2%)	90 (100.0%)	
Total	116 (58.0%)	84 (42.0%)	200 (100.0%)	

TABLE NO 2: Distribution for frequency of diastolic dysfunction with regard to age.

AGE (in years)	Dysfunction		Total
	Yes	No	
40-45	14 (45.2%)	17 (54.8%)	31 (100%)
46-50	33 (52.4%)	30 (47.6%)	63 (100%)
51-55	69 (65.1%)	37(34.9%)	106 (100%)
Total	116(58%)	84(42%)	200 (100%)

TABLE NO 3: Distribution for frequency of diastolic dysfunction with regard duration of DM

Duration of DM (in years)	Dysfunction		Total
	Yes	No	
4-9	58 (46%)	68 (54%)	126 (100%)
10-14	58 (78.4%)	16 (21.6%)	74 (100%)
Total	116 (58%)	84 (42%)	200 (100%)

TABLE NO 4: Distribution for frequency of diastolic dysfunction with regard to smoker

	Dysfunction		Total
	Yes	No	
Smoker	63 (75.0%)	21 (25.0%)	84
Non smoker	53 (45.7%)	63 (54.3%)	116
Total	116 (58%)	84 (42%)	200

TABLE NO 5: Distribution for frequency of diastolic dysfunction with regard to BMI

	Dysfunction		Total
	Yes	No	
BMI \leq 30	73 (62.9%)	64 (76.2%)	137 (68.5%)
BMI > 30	43 (37.1%)	20 (23.8%)	63 (31.5%)
Total	116 (100%)	84 (100%)	200 (100%)

TABLE NO 6: Patients characteristics with respect to distribution of diastolic dysfunction

Variables		Diastolic dysfunction	
		Yes	No
		116 (58%)	84 (42%)
Gender	Male	64 (58.2%)	46 (41.8%)
	Female	52 (57.8%)	38 (42.2%)
Age	40-45 years	14 (45.2%)	17 (54.8%)
	46-50 years	33 (52.4%)	30 (47.6%)
	51-55 years	69 (65.1%)	37 (34.9%)
Diabetes duration	4-9 years	58 (46%)	68 (54%)
	10-14 years	58 (78.4%)	16 (21.6%)
BMI	\leq 30	73 (62.9%)	64 (76.2%)
	> 30	43 (3.1%)	20 (23.8%)
Smoker		63 (75%)	21(25%)

DISCUSSION:

Cardiovascular disease (CVD) currently accounts for nearly half of the noncommunicable diseases (NCDs). NCDs have overtaken communicable diseases as the world's major disease burden, with CVD remaining the leading global cause of death, accounting for 17.3 million deaths per year, a number that is expected to grow to > 23.6 million by 2030⁸.

It is stated that diastolic heart failure is a clinical syndrome in which patients have symptoms and signs of HF, normal or near normal left ventricular (LV) ejection fraction (EF), normal or near normal LV volume and evidence of diastolic dysfunction (e.g., abnormal pattern of LV filling and elevated filling pressures. The prevalence of heart failure with preserved ejection fraction (HF-PEF) and diastolic heart failure increases with age⁹.

We did this study on patients with type II DM to see the frequency of asymptomatic diastolic dysfunction with normal left ventricular systolic function and to help us find high risk patients who need early intervention & more aggressive treatment thus reducing the morbidity and mortality.

In our study, 15.50% (n=31) patients were between 40-45 years, 31.50% (n=63) were between 46-50 years and 53% (n=106) were between 51-55 years of age, mean age of our study population was calculated as 49.84±4.2 years, 55% (n=110) were male and 45% (n=90) were females.

Diastolic dysfunction is the most prominent characteristic of diabetic cardiomyopathy. The Framingham study firmly established the epidemiologic link between diabetes and heart failure¹⁰. Frequency of diastolic dysfunction was recorded in 58% (n=116) while 42% (n=84) had no diastolic dysfunction.

We found agreement of our findings with a study done by Virendra C. Patil et al the diastolic dysfunction was 54.33% and had a higher prevalence of diastolic dysfunction in patients with longer duration of diabetes mellitus⁸. Further study by Poirier P et al found 60% diastolic dysfunction in patients¹², which is higher than our study. Another study of Patil MB et al reported higher diastolic dysfunction in patients of diabetes mellitus as 64%⁷, showed dissimilar results probably due to small sample size. It is well observed that asymptomatic diastolic heart failure. Our results showed that the trend toward diastolic dysfunction was found to be higher in 51-55 age groups as 65.1%. The prevalence and severity of diastolic dysfunction increases with age and the development or worsening of diastolic dysfunction

is associated with an increase risk of HF¹¹. Unfortunately, limited studies has been carried out in Pakistan. Our study is the first of its kind in Pakistan to evaluate the frequency of asymptomatic diastolic dysfunction in type II diabetic patients. Our study showed higher prevalence of asymptomatic diastolic dysfunction in type II diabetes mellitus. This study guided us that patients having asymptomatic diabetes mellitus should undergo echocardiography for diastolic dysfunction evaluation, should be treated for diastolic dysfunction to reduce morbidity and mortality associated with diastolic dysfunction causing diabetic cardiomyopathy.

CONCLUSION:

Overall prevalence of diastolic dysfunction is high in type 2 diabetic patients. Diastolic dysfunction is more prevalent in patients who had prolonged duration of diabetes mellitus. The early diagnosis and treatment for diastolic dysfunction must be instituted to reduce morbidity and improve the outcome of diastolic heart failure.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The Authors declare that they have no conflict of interests.

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